

Developing Scientific Research
with Ethics and Integrity

BOOKLET

Why Trust in Science Matters For Policy

Effective policymaking depends on a strong science-society relationship. The VERITY Protocol offers actionable recommendations to help policymakers as core Stewards of Trust to bridge science, society, and governance through the ecosystem of trust in science. It prioritises collaboration, benefit sharing, transparency, inclusivity, and accountability.

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1 Problem Statement

Public trust in science is crucial for promoting scientific progress, strengthening democratic institutions, and enabling informed decision-making. However, this trust is increasingly being challenged in today's society. The COVID-19 pandemic has exposed significant **public scepticism** towards vaccinations and has raised concerns about broader societal issues, including health, climate change, AI and 5G technology. These patterns of social and individual resistance stem from a **complex interplay of factors**. The spread of mis/disinformation, perceived ethical and safety concerns, as well as emerging political and ideological influences, all contribute to this mistrust.

As scientific research becomes **more global and collaborative**, particularly through digital and AI-driven methods, traditional conceptions of trust in science, once rooted in institutional **accountability and centralised expert authority**, are no longer sufficient. The well documented shift from institutional trust to **distributed trust**, driven by social media, citizen science, and private corporations' involvement, has diversified the actors and networks involved in trust-building (Botsman, 2017; van Dijk & Alinejad, 2020; Thunert, 2021), leading to new risks and opportunities in how trust is negotiated and settled.

In response to these challenges, the EU-funded VERITY project^[1] identifies the urgent need for redefining and fostering **the ecosystem of trust in science**, research, and innovation through a systemic approach. To address this challenge, it develops a **Protocol offering actionable recommendations and practical tools to 'Stewards of Trust' (SOTs)**, those who mediate between science and society. Grounded in comprehensive empirical research, extensive literature reviews, data science, and well-established conceptual frameworks, VERITY is positioned to deepen the collaborative relationship between science and society.

¹ VERITY (2022-2025; Grant Agreement 101058623) is an EU-funded project aimed at strengthening public trust in science by exploring the ecosystem of trust in science and the roles and responsibilities of various actors as Stewards of Trust. The project develops tools and recommendations to combat mis/disinformation and foster a more ethical and trustworthy research and innovation environment across Europe.

2 Why VERITY Matters

In contemporary society, characterised by epistemic uncertainty, competing sources of information, and the increasing privatisation and politicisation of knowledge, maintaining and enhancing trust in science has become a **matter of public urgency** (Nasr, 2021). While recent studies show that public trust in science remains relatively high (Wellcome Global Monitor, 2021; European Commission, 2025), this trust does not consistently translate into **acceptance of science-based recommendations or policies** (Ratner & Riis, 2014). This disconnect occurs within an increasingly **complex ecosystem of trust**, where traditional actors such as academic institutions and government agencies are now joined by newer, influential players including social media platforms, citizen science initiatives, international cross-sector research consortia and private sector stakeholders, all of whom shape public perceptions of science.

Historically, trust in science has been viewed as a relationship involving **three key components**: the person who trusts (the truster), the one being trusted (the trustee), and the subject of trust. In this framework, the public was often seen as a passive recipient of expert and scientific knowledge. However, trust is not simply a byproduct of effective communication and education; it is a fundamental element embedded in research design, governance, and the manner of communication (Origgi, 2022; Bromme & Hendriks, 2022). Building **trust across these areas** is essential for science to reach its full potential in society.

Therefore, trust should be understood as a **relational and context-dependent process**. It must also be earned rather than assumed (Goldenberg, 2021). The shift from an **'information age' to a 'reputation age'** (Origgi, 2017) has introduced new vulnerabilities, as trust in expertise becomes more diffuse, distributed across a web of actors, and increasingly fragile (Thunert, 2021). This means that scientific institutions are expected not only to demonstrate technical competence but also to maintain **transparency, accountability, and responsiveness** to societal concerns.

Trust building is further complicated by the more evident and influencing entanglement of science **with political and economic interests** (Rathenau Institute, 2021), as well as rising concerns about research integrity in an era of rapid technological advancement (European Commission, 2024). Disinformation campaigns and polarised public debates combined with the growing influence of non-traditional media have disrupted longstanding trust relationships. In this evolving landscape, understanding and reinforcing trust in science requires a rethinking of its foundations. Science and science policy must adapt to a **new social contract**, one that recognises the active role of the public and the complexity of the trust networks in which scientific knowledge circulates.

The VERITY strategic approach: building an ecosystem of trust

The VERITY project goes beyond diagnosing the problem of declining trust in science. It actively designs mechanisms to repair and reinforce it. Central to this mission is the **VERITY Protocol**, which develops a comprehensive framework of recommendations for fostering trust in science and serves as a practical guide for 'Stewards of Trust' (SOTs).

One of VERITY's key innovations is the introduction of the concept of '**Stewards of Trust**' — a diverse group of actors responsible for shaping, monitoring, and sustaining trust in science. VERITY conceptualises SOTs into eight categories based on the role they play in the ecosystem of trust:

SOT's roles	Definitions
Science Production	SOTs that focus on conducting research, producing new knowledge, and developing scientific innovations, such as universities and research institutions.
Science Education	SOTs that engage in teaching scientific knowledge in formal and informal settings, such as schools, universities, and other education institutions at various levels.
Science Communication	SOTs that share scientific information with diverse audiences through journalism, public outreach, or scientific publications, such as academic publishers, traditional and social media organisations.
Science Policy	SOTs that create, advise on, or implement policies related to science, research, and innovation, such as legislative branches and regulatory agencies, think tanks, science advisory boards and councils, international policy organisations.
Science Funding and Advocacy	SOTs that provide financial resources and supports scientific research through advocacy or funding bodies, such as public and private funding institutions.
Science Implementation	SOTs that apply scientific findings to practical or operational contexts, such as industry institutions, technology transfer offices, incubators and accelerators.
Science Oversight and Protection	SOTs that ensure that scientific research adheres to ethical, legal, and safety standards, such as research ethics and integrity committees, compliance and auditing bodies.
Science-society Facilitation and Citizen-science	SOTs that engage the public in scientific initiatives and fosters collaboration between scientists and society, such as civil society organisations (CSOs), science advocacy groups, and community advisory boards.

For SOTs, VERITY offers a roadmap for embedding **trustworthiness** into the very fabric of scientific practice, not as an afterthought, but as a foundational element and collaborative approach to the research process. This approach aligns with a broader transformation in European research policy that prioritises **societal relevance, responsibility, and reflexivity** at the core of the scientific mission (European Commission, 2021).

SOTs interact with one another and with citizens within the dynamic **ecosystem of trust**, i.e. the conceptual space within which societal trust in science is constructed, negotiated, enhanced or reduced, as well as science-society co-creation and open science are sought. At its heart, VERITY is a response to a crucial truth: **trust in science matters**. And this trust is not a fixed or abstract ideal, it is a **dynamic and negotiated process**. By adopting an **ecosystemic perspective**, VERITY equips SOTs with the tools and frameworks needed to better understand, navigate, and reinforce the evolving relationship between science and society in the 21st century.

ECOSYSTEM OF TRUST

A. TRUSTER

B. TRUSTEE

C. METHODS, TOOLS & APPROACHES TO ENHANCING TRUST IN SCIENCE

3 Summary of Findings

Who are the TRUSTERS, and what defines them?

Evidence shows that conservative **political views and strong religious commitment** are associated with **lower trust in science**, while a high interest in science and a reflexive mindset correlate with greater trust. Gender and education effects remain inconclusive and context-dependent. Other influential factors include belief in conspiracy theories, geographic location, and experiences of marginalisation. These findings highlight that trust is contingent on social identities and belief systems, underscoring the need for tailored, inclusive approaches to fostering trust in science.

WHOM do people trust?

VERITY findings highlight that trust in science is shaped by both **individual and institutional actors**. **Scientists and researchers** are the most trusted figures, especially when perceived as competent, honest, benevolent, and open. **Public sector scientists** and those practicing open science or engaging in co-creation are generally seen as more trustworthy.

Trust is also bolstered when scientists communicate their own research or are affiliated with **prestigious institutions**. **Higher education institutions** foster trust through their role in science education, promoting critical thinking and connecting science to everyday life.

Opinion leaders, such as influencers, activists, and informed citizens, can enhance trust by making science relatable and accessible to wider audiences. **Governments and policymakers** are crucial to institutional trust, particularly through science policy, communication, and oversight. However, public trust in these actors is context-dependent and varies with political circumstances

WHAT do people trust?

VERITY findings show that public trust in science is closely tied to the **quality, transparency, and integrity of scientific practices**. High-quality research, especially when free from misconduct, is seen as essential. **Publicly funded research** is generally perceived as more trustworthy than privately funded work, due to its transparency and public accountability.

Co-creation and participatory processes, where citizens engage meaningfully in the production and evaluation of science, can build trust, though perceptions vary. Open science practices, including accessible and transparent methods, also enhance credibility and public confidence.

Effective science communication is a critical trust-builder. Clear, balanced messaging (especially when accompanied by ethical considerations, credible sources, and audience-specific framing or targeting strategies) has been

shown to positively influence public trust. Communication that connects scientific content to personal values, motivations, or real-world relevance is particularly effective.

HOW is trust built?

The VERITY Protocol identifies **six overarching strategies** to foster trust in science, including Building Trustworthy Science, Engaging the Public in Scientific Processes, Educating and Raising Awareness, Science Communication, Building Supportive Policy Frameworks, and Collaboration. The key takeaways of the VERITY Protocol include:

Trustworthy Science

Promote scientific rigour, open science, inclusivity, benefit sharing, ethics and research integrity. Improve transparency on funding sources and enhance independent research validation.

Public Engagement

Involve citizens as co-creators in research, from design to implementation. Promote inclusivity and fair recognition of public contributions in science.

Education & Awareness

Integrate digital literacy and critical evaluation skills into formal education to counter mis/disinformation, reduce echo chambers, and promote exposure to credible information. Develop public campaigns to explain the scientific method and societal benefits of science.

Science Communication

Reform academic incentives to reward science communication and public engagement. Train researchers and journalists in clear, culturally aware science communication and crisis messaging.

Supportive Policy Frameworks

Design evidence-informed policies that prioritise benefit sharing, transparency, inclusivity, and accountability. Avoid selective use of science to support political agendas.

Collaboration

Create mechanisms for interdisciplinary, international, and multi-stakeholder collaboration. Foster a coordinated, innovative, and impactful science ecosystem built on trust and mutual benefit.

Each Steward of Trust (SOT) plays a critical role in implementing these strategies and recommendations. The VERITY Protocol highlights this interconnected ecosystem, by demonstrating that:

- SOTs are interdependent in their efforts to support public trust in science.
- Each SOT plays multiple roles and holds various responsibilities in fostering trust in science.
- Collaboration between all SOTs is essential for achieving public trust.

Science Funding and Advocacy

Science Policy

Science Implementation

Science Communication

Science Oversight and Protection

Science-Society Facilitation and Citizen Science

Science Production

Science Education

Science Funding and Advocacy

Science Policy

Science Communication

Science Implementation

Educating and Raising Awareness

Engaging the Public in Scientific Processes

Science Communication

COLLABORATION

Building Supportive Policy Frameworks

Building Trustworthy Science

Science Oversight and Protection

Science-Society Facilitation and Citizen Science

Science Production

Science Education

4 Call for Action

Public trust in science is not a given; it must be built, sustained, and protected through **collective action**. The **VERITY Protocol provides a roadmap for this transformation**, with clear, coordinated recommendations, underscoring the importance of **collaboration at every level**. We call on all SOTs in the science-society ecosystem to play an active role in this endeavour:

- I. **For research institutions and scientists: REIMAGINE SUCCESS.** Science must be accountable to society, and institutions should value social impact alongside traditional academic achievements. As research institutions and responsible, you should shift incentives to reward meaningful engagement and public-facing science communication. Foster interdisciplinary collaboration and cross-sector partnerships and prioritise the development of robust infrastructures that support effective communication, empowering researchers to engage the public without compromising their scientific integrity.
- II. **For science educators and communicators: TRANSLATE COMPLEXITY INTO CLARITY.** Science educators and communicators play a pivotal role in making science relatable and accessible. Simplify without oversimplifying. Use creative, tailored strategies to convey complex topics clearly, ensuring that science is understandable to all while promoting critical thinking. Counter mis/disinformation and empower diverse audiences to engage with science in meaningful ways. Collaboration with trusted influencers, educators, and ambassadors can bridge gaps and amplify science's relevance in everyday life.
- III. **For policymakers and funders: LEAD BY EXAMPLE.** We urge policymakers and funders to embed trust-building as a core policy goal. This requires not only sustainable funding and strong governance and legal frameworks, but also an unwavering commitment to foster ethical, inclusive, and transparent science practices. Recognise and reward the value of public engagement and scientific transparency, ensuring that science serves the public good, not special or corporate interests.
- IV. **For industry and science implementors: BUILD TRUST THROUGH ACCOUNTABILITY.** Industry leaders and science implementors are key actors in transforming scientific knowledge into real-world solutions. Uphold transparency and promote independent validation to ensure credibility. Address conflicts of interest openly and ethically, especially in privately funded research. Engage collaboratively with other SOTs to foster a robust ecosystem of trustworthy science. Demonstrate clear, measurable societal benefits of scientific innovations, reinforcing the value of science through tangible outcomes.

V. Science oversight and monitoring institutions: SAFEGUARD INTEGRITY THROUGH ETHICAL LEADERSHIP. Oversight and monitoring institutions are essential in upholding the ethical foundations of science. Develop and enforce robust, adaptive practices that ensure research integrity across disciplines and sectors. Deliver ethics training that is both practical and impactful, fostering a culture of responsibility. Maintain rigorous oversight for all research (whether publicly funded, privately funded, or supported through public-private partnerships) and adapt quality assurance mechanisms to evolving global contexts.

VI. For citizens and civil society organisations: ENGAGE, QUESTION, AND CO-CREATE. Trustworthy science thrives through the active participation of citizens. Science needs your voice, your knowledge, and your engagement. Engage with scientific discussions, constructively question findings, and be part of co-creating solutions and research activities. Your participation ensures that science aligns with public interests and is shaped by societal needs. It is only through your involvement that science can remain relevant, transparent, and inclusive.

For all stakeholders: TRUST IS EVERYONE'S BUSINESS. We all have a role in cultivating trust in science. Whether through co-creation, public participation, or mutual learning, every view and action counts. We must prioritise creating inclusive spaces where diverse voices are heard, and science can thrive in dialogue with society. Through ongoing **collaboration and dialogue**, we can build a more resilient, trusted, and impactful scientific community.

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